

APPLICATION OF CONFORMAL GEOMETRIC ALGEBRA TO IN-PLANE ROTATED FACE DETECTION BY ADABOOST-BASED ALGORITHM

ABSTRACT. Viola and Jones proposed for face detection a state-of-the-art method with respect to performance and robustness, using the AdaBoost algorithm. In this paper, we extend this method by utilizing Conformal Geometric Algebra (CGA) to extract feature values after using Haar-like patterns. For evaluation, we apply CGA with a different number of Haar-like patterns to construct a feature and the accuracy is then compared to choose the one that works best in practice. Moreover, we raise the efficiency of the integral image representation by introducing non-integer sized patterns. Overall, we can obtain more informative features that substantially enhance system performance.

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1. INTRODUCTION

There has been a variety of approaches and solutions for face detection problems. Viola and Jones proposed the state-of-the-art method in [13, 12] which gained success in both performance and robustness. Their method is based on the AdaBoost algorithm which is simple to implement and is efficient for obtaining high accuracy. Inspired by their work, a number of methods have been proposed to advance face detection systems.

In this paper, we build on the work of Viola-Jones and propose a new method to apply AdaBoost. There are two main contributions in our approach, they are briefly introduced below and in detail in the next sections.

First, we utilize Conformal Geometric Algebra (CGA) [11, 1, 3] to extract feature values after using Haar-like patterns. The procedure to calculate feature values follows [6]. To evaluate the performance of our proposed method, we apply CGA with different number of Haar-like patterns to construct a feature and the accuracy is then compared to choose the one that works best in practice (see also Section 3.3).

Second, integral image representation is utilized more efficiently by using non-integer size patterns. Compared to the original method, we can obtain more informative features that enhance the system performance.

2. REVIEW OF VIOLA-JONES ALGORITHM

2.1. Haar-like Patterns. Accuracy and robustness have a strong relation to how features are extracted and used. Viola and Jones applied Haar-like features to find pixel level differences in an image region. Examples of Haar-like patterns are shown below in Fig. 1.

FIGURE 1. Haar-like rectangle patterns used by Viola and Jones.

2.2. AdaBoost Algorithm. For this problem, AdaBoost [9, 10] can be used to select the essential features as well as to train for a strong classifier. This algorithm constructs a strong classifier from a linear combination of weak classifiers.

$$(1) \quad F(x) = \sum_{t=1}^T \alpha_t h_t(x),$$

where x is an image example, $h_t(x)$ is a weak or basic classifier. Normally, the set \mathcal{H} of all classifiers $h(x)$ is finite.

A weak classifier is a function of a feature f , a threshold θ and a polarity p that denotes the direction of the inequality:

$$(2) \quad h(x, f, p, \theta) = \begin{cases} 1 & p \times f(x) < p \times \theta, \\ 0 & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases}$$

θ and p are determined for a particular feature to best classify positive and negative examples. In the Viola-Jones system, supposing that there are N image examples, K features for each image, and M being the number of trained weak classifiers, the total complexity for training is $O(MKN \log_2 N)$. However, all feature values for the whole input image set should be pre-calculated and stored in the hard drive. This leads to a waste of preparation time as well as memory consumption.

3. PROPOSED METHOD BY CONFORMAL GEOMETRIC ALGEBRA

3.1. New Haar-like Value Extraction. In this paper, we propose to use Haar-like rectangles with non-integer size. With this method, we can obtain more informative Haar-like patterns. Thus, in the training procedure, better classifiers can be chosen and yield higher classification rates. Fig. 2 shows some examples of new non integer-sized rectangles. In this example, Tab. 1 shows 3×3 Haar-like patterns (type (b) in Fig. 1) applied to a 3×4 sub-window image. Numbers inside each cell indicate the gray level of pixels for demonstration purpose.

15	12	15	21
10	5	5	16
12	8	3	6

FIGURE 2. 3×4 sub-window image with non integer-sized feature

TABLE 1. Color map for Haar-like type (b), white region denoted by 1 otherwise -1 .

1	-1	1
1	-1	1
1	-1	1

By using the color map above, feature values are quickly computed with integer or non-integer size Haar-like pattern with the complexity of $O(1)$.

3.2. Review of Conformal Geometric Algebra. Conformal Geometric Algebra (CGA) [2, 3, 4] extends the real Euclidean vector space \mathbb{R}^m by adding two orthonormal basis vectors. It results in the space determined by $m + 2$ basis vectors $\{\mathbf{e}_1, \mathbf{e}_2, \dots, \mathbf{e}_m, \mathbf{e}_+, \mathbf{e}_-\}$ and its Clifford algebra, termed CGA.

In CGA, a real Euclidean vector $\mathbf{x} = \sum_i^m x_i \mathbf{e}_i \in \mathbb{R}^m$ is mapped to a vector $X \in \mathcal{G}_{m+1,1}$ by

$$(3) \quad X = \mathbf{x} + \frac{1}{2} \|\mathbf{x}\|^2 \mathbf{e}_\infty + \mathbf{e}_0.$$

The general form of a conformal vector S in $\mathcal{G}_{m+1,1}$ for hyper-planes and hyper-spheres is

$$(4) \quad S = \mathbf{s} + s_\infty \mathbf{e}_\infty + s_0 \mathbf{e}_0,$$

where $\mathbf{s} = \sum_i^m s_i \mathbf{e}_i$ is a vector in the real Euclidean space \mathbb{R}^m . s_∞ and s_0 are scalar coefficients.

A sphere in CGA is defined as:

$$(5) \quad S = X - \frac{1}{2} r^2 \mathbf{e}_\infty = \mathbf{x} + \frac{1}{2} \{\|\mathbf{x}\|^2 - r^2\} \mathbf{e}_\infty + \mathbf{e}_0,$$

where \mathbf{x} and r are the center and radius of the sphere in real Euclidean space \mathbb{R}^m respectively, with $P \in S \Leftrightarrow P \cdot S = 0$ for any conformal point P .

Similarly, a plane can be expressed as a conformal vector in CGA:

$$(6) \quad \pi = \mathbf{n} + d \mathbf{e}_\infty,$$

where $\mathbf{n} \in \mathbb{R}^m$ is the normal vector, and $X \in \pi \Leftrightarrow X \cdot \pi = 0 \Leftrightarrow \mathbf{n} \cdot \mathbf{x} + d = 0$ in real space \mathbb{R}^m , and d the oriented scalar distance from the origin.

3.3. Applying Conformal Geometric Algebra to AdaBoost. In the Viola-Jones system, only one Haar-like feature for each weak classifier is used and in each round, the whole set of features is put into the comparison to choose the best one which achieves the lowest error. Theoretically, AdaBoost can be applied to search for the best weak classifiers in this way. However, there is still room to further improve and benefit even more from Haar-like features and the power of AdaBoost.

In most of the recent research on face detection with AdaBoost using Haar-like patterns as features, the features have not been efficiently mined because the main purpose is just to obtain the smallest error without analyzing the data representation. Thus, in this paper, we propose to apply CGA to face detection. The key point in our method is to figure out the best hyper-plane (or hyper-sphere) that fits all feature values calculated from input images. For this problem, we use results from [6] and we propose a new method to estimate a hyper-sphere or hyper-plane that best fits to a set of points by using CGA.

Mathematically, we assume a set of points $\mathcal{X} = \{\mathbf{x}_k = \sum_i^m x_{k,i} \mathbf{e}_i \in \mathbb{R}^m, k = 1, \dots, n\}$. By transforming each Euclidean point to a point in CGA space, we obtain in $\mathcal{G}_{m+1,1}$ the set

$$(7) \quad \mathcal{P} = \{X_k = \mathbf{x}_k + \frac{1}{2} \|\mathbf{x}_k\|^2 \mathbf{e}_\infty + \mathbf{e}_0, k = 1, \dots, n\}.$$

This set of points \mathcal{P} is approximated to fit the hyper-sphere (or -plane) represented by the conformal vector $S = \mathbf{s} + s_\infty \mathbf{e}_\infty + s_0 \mathbf{e}_0$ in $\mathcal{G}_{m+1,1}$. The problem is solved by minimizing the error function E defined as

$$(8) \quad E = \sum_{k=1}^n d^2(X_k, S) = \sum_{k=1}^n (\mathbf{x}_k \cdot \mathbf{s} - s_\infty - \frac{1}{2} \|\mathbf{x}_k\|^2 s_0)^2$$

where $d(X, S)$ is the distance between point X and the hyper-plane (or hyper-sphere) S , and it is proportional to the inner product of P and S

$$(9) \quad \begin{aligned} d(X, S) &\propto X \cdot S \\ &= (\mathbf{x} + \frac{1}{2} \|\mathbf{x}\|^2 \mathbf{e}_\infty + \mathbf{e}_0) \cdot (\mathbf{s} + s_\infty \mathbf{e}_\infty + s_0 \mathbf{e}_0) \\ &= \mathbf{x} \cdot \mathbf{s} - s_\infty - \frac{1}{2} \|\mathbf{x}\|^2 s_0. \end{aligned}$$

The solution to this problem has clearly been proven and explained in [6] by using the eigen decomposition for

$$(10) \quad \mathbf{A} \mathbf{s} = \lambda \mathbf{s}.$$

In this problem, an eigen vector \mathbf{s} is an eigen vector of the matrix \mathbf{A} used to represent the hyper-plane (or hyper-sphere) $S = \mathbf{s} + s_\infty \mathbf{e}_\infty + s_0 \mathbf{e}_0$ that fits the input point set, and the eigen-value λ is the variance or the sum of the squared distances between X_k and S . The matrix \mathbf{A} is defined as

$$(11) \quad \mathbf{A} = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{k=1}^n \mathbf{f}(\mathbf{x}_k) (\mathbf{f}(\mathbf{x}_k))^T,$$

where

$$(12) \quad \begin{aligned} \mathbf{f}(\mathbf{x}) &= \mathbf{x} - \mathbf{f}_\infty - \|\mathbf{x}\|^2 \mathbf{f}_0 \in \mathbb{R}^m, \\ \mathbf{f}_\infty &= \frac{-\sigma_4 \sum_{k=1}^n \mathbf{x}_k + \sigma_2 \sum_{k=1}^n \|\mathbf{x}_k\|^2 \mathbf{x}_k}{(\sigma_2)^2 - n\sigma_4}, \\ \mathbf{f}_0 &= \frac{\sigma_2 \sum_{k=1}^n \mathbf{x}_k - n \sum_{k=1}^n \|\mathbf{x}_k\|^2 \mathbf{x}_k}{(\sigma_2)^2 - n\sigma_4}. \end{aligned}$$

with the extra parameters: $\sigma_2 = \sum_{k=1}^n \|\mathbf{x}_k\|^2$ and $\sigma_4 = \sum_{k=1}^n \|\mathbf{x}_k\|^4$. The coefficients s_∞ and s_0 are calculated from the vectors \mathbf{f}_∞ and \mathbf{f}_0 as

$$(13) \quad s_\infty = \mathbf{f}_\infty \cdot \mathbf{s}, \quad \frac{1}{2} s_0 = \mathbf{f}_0 \cdot \mathbf{s}.$$

To apply to AdaBoost, instead of using only one Haar-like feature as in the Viola-Jones system, we combine two Haar-like values to construct a point \mathbf{x}_k for every input example. From that, the set of input examples used for training is $\mathcal{X} = \{\mathbf{x}_k = \sum_i^m x_{k,i} \mathbf{e}_i \in \mathbb{R}^m\}$ and Boolean variable $y_i \in \{0, 1\}$ for non-face and face examples (indicated with index c below), respectively.

For each subset of non-face and face examples, a hyper-sphere (or -plane) should be estimated using the formulas in [6]. After solving for eigen vector \mathbf{s}_p, λ_p and \mathbf{s}_n, λ_n for face and non-face cluster, probabilities that an input example happens to be in each cluster are calculated according to the following probability formulas that are fully specified in [6].

The density function that a point \mathbf{x} belongs to any of the hyper-shape clusters denoted by $S_{c,l} = \mathbf{s}_{c,l} + s_{\infty c,l} \mathbf{e}_{\infty} + s_{0c,l} \mathbf{e}_0$, $l \in \{1, \dots, m\}$ with eigen-values $\lambda_{c,l}$ is

$$(14) \quad \Pr(\mathbf{x} | \lambda_{c,l}) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2\pi\lambda_{c,l}}} \exp\left(-\frac{d^2(X, S_{c,l})}{2\lambda_{c,l}}\right).$$

The posterior probability density function for \mathbf{x} , given the cluster $y = c$, is

$$(15) \quad \Pr(\mathbf{x} | c) = \prod_l^m \Pr(\mathbf{x} | \lambda_{c,l}).$$

This posterior probability is used for the classification process, by comparing the probability that an example belongs to each cluster.

$$(16) \quad h(\mathbf{x}, S_p, \lambda_p, S_n, \lambda_n) = \begin{cases} 1 & \Pr(\mathbf{x} | 1) > \Pr(\mathbf{x} | 0), \\ 0 & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases}$$

Our proposed method is clearly shown in the following Alg. 1. CGA eigen-values and eigen-vectors are solved for by Alg. 2. The best single feature for CGA of a 1-D space is found by applying Alg. 3.

Algorithm 1 AdaBoost with proposed CGA method

Require: input examples $(x_1, y_1), (x_2, y_2), \dots, (x_N, y_N)$ where y_i is 1 or 0 for positive and negative examples respectively

Ensure: final strong classifier

- 1: Initialize weights $w = \frac{1}{2_{pos}}, \frac{1}{2_{neg}}$ for positive and negative example respectively
- 2: **for** $t \leftarrow 1, T$ **do**
- 3: Normalize weights: $w_{t,i} \leftarrow \frac{w_{t,i}}{\sum_{j=1}^N w_{t,j}}$
- 4: Apply Alg. 3 $m - 1$ times to find 1 best single feature
- 5: Construct $(m - 1)$ -dimensional \mathbf{x} from $m - 1$ best single features
- 6: Select K' features from full set of features
- 7: **for** each of K' features **do**
- 8: Compute feature values for every example to construct \mathbf{x} in m dimensions
- 9: Apply Alg. 2 to find eigen-value λ_p, λ_n and eigen vectors $\mathbf{s}_p, \mathbf{s}_n$
- 10: Define conformal vectors for the hyper-plane (or hyper-sphere) s of non-face and face regions:

$$S_p = \mathbf{s}_p + s_{\infty p} \mathbf{e}_{\infty} + s_{0p} \mathbf{e}_0, \quad S_n = \mathbf{s}_n + s_{\infty n} \mathbf{e}_{\infty} + s_{0n} \mathbf{e}_0$$

- 11: Compute the posterior probability for each \mathbf{x} to be in a face and non-face region:

$$\Pr(\mathbf{x} | c) = \prod_l^m \Pr(\mathbf{x} | \lambda_{c,l})$$

- 12: Select the best weak classifier that minimizes error:

$$\varepsilon_t = \min_{\mathbf{x}, S_p, \lambda_p, S_n, \lambda_n} \sum_i w_i | h(\mathbf{x}, S_p, \lambda_p, S_n, \lambda_n) - y_i |$$

- 13: Define $h_t(\mathbf{x}) = h(\mathbf{x}, S'_p, \lambda'_p, S'_n, \lambda'_n)$ where $S'_p, \lambda'_p, S'_n, \lambda'_n$ are minimizers of ε_t

- 14: Calculate $\alpha_t \leftarrow \ln\left(\frac{1-\varepsilon_t}{\varepsilon_t}\right)$

- 15: **end for**

- 16: Update weights: $w_{t+1,i} \leftarrow w_t \left(\frac{1}{\alpha_t}\right)^{1-e_i}$ where $e_i = 0$ if correct, otherwise 1

- 17: **end for**

- 18: Combine final strong classifier $C(x) \leftarrow \begin{cases} 1 & \sum_{t=1}^T \alpha_t h_t(x) \geq \frac{1}{2} \sum_{t=1}^T \alpha_t \\ 0 & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases}$
-

Algorithm 2 Compute eigen value and conformal eigen vector**Require:** set of points $\mathcal{X} = \{\mathbf{x}_k = \sum_i^m x_{k,i} \mathbf{e}_i \in \mathbb{R}^m, k = 1, \dots, n\}$ **Ensure:** eigen-value λ and conformal eigen vector \mathbf{s}

- 1: Compute σ_2 and σ_4
- 2: Compute \mathbf{f}_∞ and \mathbf{f}_0
- 3: Compute $\mathbf{f}(\mathbf{x})$: $\mathbf{f}(\mathbf{x}) = \mathbf{x} - \mathbf{f}_\infty - \|\mathbf{x}\|^2 \mathbf{f}_0$
- 4: Construct matrix $\mathbf{A} = \frac{1}{2} \sum_{k=1}^n \mathbf{f}(\mathbf{x}_k) (\mathbf{f}(\mathbf{x}_k))^T$
- 5: Solve eigen decomposition problem: $\mathbf{A}\mathbf{s} = \lambda\mathbf{s}$
- 6: Compute parameters s_∞ and s_0 : $s_\infty = \mathbf{f}_\infty \cdot \mathbf{s}$, $\frac{1}{2}s_0 = \mathbf{f}_0 \cdot \mathbf{s}$

Algorithm 3 Select best single feature for 1-D CGA**Require:** input examples $(x_1, y_1), (x_2, y_2), \dots, (x_N, y_N)$ where y_i is 1 or 0 for positive and negative examples respectively**Ensure:** best single feature

- 1: Select K' features from full set of features
- 2: **for** each of the K' features **do**
- 3: Compute feature values for every example to construct a 1-dimensional \mathbf{x}
- 4: Apply Alg. 2 to find eigen-values λ_p, λ_n and eigen vectors $\mathbf{s}_p, \mathbf{s}_n$
- 5: Define conformal vectors for the hyper-plane (or hyper-sphere) for face and non-face regions:

$$\begin{aligned} S_p &= \mathbf{s}_p + s_{\infty p} \mathbf{e}_\infty + s_{0p} \mathbf{e}_0, \\ S_n &= \mathbf{s}_n + s_{\infty n} \mathbf{e}_\infty + s_{0n} \mathbf{e}_0 \end{aligned}$$

- 6: Compute the posterior probability for each \mathbf{x} to be in a face and non-face region:

$$\Pr(\mathbf{x} | c) = \Pr(\mathbf{x} | \lambda_{c,0})$$

- 7: Select the feature that minimizes error:

$$\varepsilon = \min_{\mathbf{x}, S_p, \lambda_p, S_n, \lambda_n} \sum_i w_i |h(\mathbf{x}, S_p, \lambda_p, S_n, \lambda_n) - y_i|$$

- 8: **end for**

4. EXPERIMENTS AND RESULTS

4.1. Experiments. In training and testing processes, we use the dataset Yi-Qing [14] from the Viola-Jones system [14]. Because input images in the dataset are in the different quality of brightness and contrast, we first normalize [8] those images for both the training and testing processes. We conduct two kinds of training that are for frontal faces and in-plane rotated faces. Rotated face images are generated by rotating original frontal faces in [14] with angles varied from -60° to 60° .

Tab. 2 shows the number of face/non-face input examples we used in the training and testing process in both kinds of detection.

Our system is totally implemented from scratch in Java. We trained and tested this system on a Mac OS with 8 GB 1600MHz DDR3 of memory and a 2.6 GHz Intel Core i5 processor. As mentioned before, a hard drive is not mandatory due to the only use of RAM for experiments with our system.

Besides comparing with the Viola-Jones system, we apply CGA in different ways by varying from 1 to 3 the number of Haar-like patterns that make up a CGA point \mathbf{x} .

TABLE 2. Number of face/non-face images in Yi-Qing data set.

	Training set	Testing set
Face	2000	2916
Non-face	2000	5960
Total	4000	7960

4.2. **Results.** Fig. 3 shows the Receiver Operating Characteristic (ROC) for our proposed method and the Viola-Jones method with frontal and in-plane rotated face datasets. Three versions of CGA are involved in this experiment. As shown in the figure, our systems with CGA achieves higher curves that denote better classification rates compared to the Viola-Jones method.

FIGURE 3. ROC for frontal and in-plane rotated face detection.

Experiments show our proposed method achieves lower error rates than the original Viola-Jones method when using the same number of weak classifiers. Furthermore, to obtain given error rates, fewer weak classifiers are required to be utilized in our new CGA method.

FIGURE 4. Histogram of feature values from 1st weak classifier by Viola-Jones method.

By experiments, we were also able to show that it is moreover sufficient to choose a few good weak classifiers and combine them to a strong one by randomly choosing a small number of features. After conducting several experiments, $K' = 5000$ is adequate for a comparable level of precision and also to reduce the training time.

Our proposed method using CGA achieves higher accuracy than the Viola-Jones approach due to the effectiveness of geometric characteristics of face and non-face distributions. The key idea of previous algorithms in the Viola-Jones system is finding the optimal threshold that best separates two distributions. However, this method proves to be inefficient when these two distributions overlap and it leads to a high level of error on the classification. To overcome this difficulty, CGA is applied to find the hyper-plane (or hyper-sphere) to best fit face and non-face regions rather than using a simple threshold.

Fig. 4 denotes the histogram for feature values computed from the first weak classifier if we apply the Viola-Jones method for the frontal face dataset. It can be clearly seen that even the best threshold can still yield a high value of error due to the large overlapping area between the two regions. In contrast, if we apply our CGA algorithm, we can achieve a much lower error value after the first round of AdaBoost. Fig. 5 shows that by using CGA for 2-D space, the two regions are mostly separated and it results in a very low error rate.

5. CONCLUSION

In this paper, we propose a novel approach for the face detection problem by applying Conformal Geometric Algebra. This method achieves as high as or higher accuracy than the Viola-Jones algorithm. Various numbers of vector space dimensions for CGA were experimented with to figure out which one is most practical for achieving the best detection rates in both frontal and in-plane rotated face detection.

Furthermore, the integral image technique is improved in this paper, and results in an enhancement on feature mining for training weak classifiers and the detection accuracy is higher as well.

We also proved that a small set of randomly selected features is enough for developing a strong classifier with similar detection rate. By using this realization, the training time is significantly reduced as well as system performance improved.

FIGURE 5. 2-D CGA density function from 1st weak classifier.

For future work, the present research may be extended and improved by applying Haar wavelets for constructing a point \mathbf{x} . For each image, we can repeatedly calculate a feature value by utilizing a Haar-like pattern, then the image can be rescaled by a predefined scaling factor and one can find the corresponding feature value again with the same Haar-like pattern. Finally, all the computed feature values can be combined to form a point \mathbf{x} , then followed by the AdaBoost algorithm as explained in this paper. The purpose of this technique would be to preserve the main characteristics of any input image after applying a Haar-like pattern while simultaneously removing unnecessary or noisy information from the image. It will therefore be more advanced and sensitive than only using several random Haar-like patterns for a point \mathbf{x} .

E.H. requests adherence to the Creative Peace License [5], when applying this research.

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